

Funding Vocational Education for Increased Productivity in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The paper assessed Funding of vocational education for increased productivity, budgetary allocation to educational sector and needs for funding and challenges of funding. Vocational education is a wheel of progress for achieving the desired technological and economic development of Nigeria. It is a tool for addressing the economic, political and social crisis threatening the political and economic stability of the nation. It is a major instrument for national development as it addresses the rising unemployment, lack of skilled workers, high crime rate, high dropout rate and movement to urban cities in search of job. For the programme to be productive and successful, funding must be sufficient because funding is a major factor that mars or make it productive. Funding in vocational education is the life-wire that other activities revolves on. The paper finally recommended that Government at all levels should provide and allocate sufficient funds to the vocational education programme sector; individual citizens should recognize and see the program as a first class educational programme that impart learners with skills, knowledge and competencies for self-reliant; only professionals with degrees in the field should control, administer and man the management of the programme for efficient and for increased productivity as non-professionals politicizes funding and activities of the programme; and government should meet the United Nations Educational Scientific and cultural organization 26% UNESCO recommendation budgetary provision.

Keywords: Funding, Vocational, Education, Increase, Productivity.

Introduction

Funding is the provision of funds or money for a person or an enterprise by organization or government for a particular purpose. Funding and Financing of vocational education is a derived investment in society. Sufficient resources investment in education will help to secure a sure development of society, because developing the learners is developing the Nation. Investing sufficient resources in education contributes to the development of both humans and society at large. Government attention is needed to be drawn on the fact that budgetary allocation for education needs to be increased continuous to meet United Nations Educational Scientific and cultural organization (UNESCO) 26% education budgetary allocation standard. Improving the budgetary allocation for the education sector will help to increase the number and quality of professionals, Lecturers and learners in the country. The dwindling budgetary allocation for education has caused severe damage to the academic performance of learners and eroded University freedom and autonomy (Mukoro in Ordu, 2017).

Funding according to Peter (2018), is the provision of financial resources in order to meet a need, project or program. Funding in general term is a way of providing both fleeting capital, fixed assets (plants and machines) for the day to day running of a business. It includes the provision of adequate labour supply, employee development and staff appraisal to meet organizational goals. The process of making the funds available to the units that require them either in the short or long run is referred to as funding. Funding according to Williams and Woke (2020), is the act of providing financial resources, usually in the form of money or other values as effort or time, to finance a need program and projects usually by an organization or company. Generally, funding is used when a firm uses its internal reserves to satisfy, its necessity for cash. Funding could come through personal savings, credit, subsidies and taxes. In the governmental education sector, the government is the sole provider of funds for the smooth running of the education sector. This is because it is directly owned, operated or managed by the government through individuals. Decisions are directly made by the government that governs the day to day running of government owned schools. Funding has the capacity and potentials of bringing an organisation out of obscurity. Funding is the life wire of every business organisation. Daso (2012) stated that the allocation of funds to the education sector as a share of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is quite minimal. Daso further opined that government funding of vocational education have not been impressive. Adequate funding and proper management of funds in business shows the progress and impact of an organisational goal attainment. In the education sector in Nigeria, under funding is still the bane of vocational education in Nigeria (Offiong et al, 2013). The road to success and developmental growth of Nigeria lies in the hands of vocational education and yet it is the worst applied instrument for national development (Dike, 2009). Literacy and numeracy alone cannot get Nigeria out of poverty. We will continue to be enslaved by world leading countries because we have nothing to offer technologically. Nigeria is a very wealthy nation that has what it takes to compete with other countries in the world but due to lack of adequate funding and provision of practical learning experiences, Nigeria is limited to theoretical vocational education.

Funding of tertiary education in Nigeria seems to be gradually fading out of federal and State governments' concern. Looking at the annual budgetary provisions for the education sector, one can easily assert that government can easily abandon tertiary Institutions to be self-sustaining (Ordu, 2017). The National Policy on Education document in Nigeria attaches great importance to Vocational Education. This is because; it is one of the prime movers for achieving the desired technological and economic development of Nigeria. It is also a tool for addressing the economic, political, and social crises that are threatening the political and economic stability of the nation (FRN 2014). Rising unemployment, lack of skilled workers, high school dropout rates and the changing demographic nature of the workforce has placed the need for vocational education high on the educational reformed agenda (Okolocha & Baba, 2016).

Vocational education is that part of the total experience whereby the individual learns knowledge and skills successfully to carry on a gainful occupation. Vocational education is also seen as a highly useful education, because its occupational content offers one the opportunity to acquire skills, attitudes, interests and knowledge to perform socially and economically work that is beneficial to the individual and the society (Ugboaja, 2016). Okon and Uke (2015), posited that the progress of a nation is the function of the level of the resourcefulness of the people which to a greater extent, relate to the level

of quality of vocational training and purposeful development of functional education in that nation. Vocational education adequately equips students to be more effective in this age of science and technology, and to raise a generation of people who can think for themselves and respect the dignity of labour and propel its citizenry into a vibrant economy. What is needed today, and tomorrow are workers with good technical skill background, rugged enough to transform Nigeria into positive technological breakthrough with the ability to meet its immediate demand. As the world around us is changing fast, there must be an increased emphasis on vocational education in meeting the aims and objectives in which it was established (Dimkpa & James, 2020).

Agwi, (2019) opined that the enterprise of manpower development is practicalized on the transfer of knowledge and skills to the trainee through education and training. Efficient and corruption free educational systems are essential component of this, for cultural, self-economic and environmentally sustainable development of individual communities and nations. Thus, any country which desires to enhance and accelerates its manpower and national development must take its vocational educational system seriously and execute it comprehensively. Vocational education is important to the development of human resources, impartation of appropriate skills, knowledge and attitudes. It is the basis for transformation, industrialization and a highway to global knowledge economy. It leads to national transformation and ensuring of peace and security. Thus, the goals of wealth creation, employment generation, poverty reduction and value re-orientation can only be attained and sustained through an efficient vocational education system which impacts the relevant skills, knowledge, capacities, attitudes and values. The scope of its contributions cut across mechanical technology, automobile technology, woodwork technology, electrical and electronic technology, building technology etc. When vocational education program succeeds, even a non-entity will observe it, and when it is failing, it will be observed also (Dimkpa & James, 2020). Vocational Education is any form of education whose primary purpose is to prepare persons for employment in recognized occupations (Okoro, 2006). Vocational education provides the skills, knowledge and attitudes necessary for effective employment in specific occupation. Any education that is necessary for effective employment in an occupation is Vocational education. Vocational education is education designed to prepare individuals or skilled personnel for one or a group of occupations, trader or jobs (Egumu et al, 2017). Vocational education is provided in special programmes offered at secondary and post-secondary levels. Vocational education is expensive education because of the tools, equipment and materials that are part of the training process. To avoid the wastage of resources, learners for Vocational education should be carefully selected to ensure that they have the interest and aptitude to benefit from the training. Those learners having the genuine interest for the occupation only that should be trained. Establishment of vocational education programmes should therefore be based on needs, the needs of the country; the needs of the community; and the needs of the individual citizens. Vocational education programmes should therefore be evaluated to find answers to the following questions: Are the individuals trained in the programme able to find employment in the occupation in which they have been trained? Are they doing well in their place of employment? Etc.

Productivity or productive efficiency is the quantitative relationship between what is produced (outputs) and the resources used in production (inputs) (Mac'odu, 2005). The inputs include labour, capital, raw materials, energy etc. while the outputs include goods and services. An enduring objective

of managers is to improve productivity thus reducing the cost per unit of output or increase output with a stable amount of inputs of labour, capital, energy materials etc. productivity is the first test of management competence (Drucker in Mac’odu, 2005).

Budgetary Allocation to Education is seen as a plan quantified in monetary terms prepared and approved for a specified period of time usually showing planned income to be generated and expended. In Nigeria, budget is normally presented by the executive arm of government to the legislative arm before it becomes appropriation bill (Ogunbenle & Edogiawerie, 2016). Vocational education as an integral part of national development required a proper funding. The percentage of allocation to education in Nigeria since 2010 till date is too poor. This has led to a decline in the quality of vocational education in Nigeria. Ameh and Aluko (2019) stated that the 2019 budget of N634.56 billions which gave 7.11% to Education has proven to all that the ruling class in Nigeria does not prioritize education. Ndujihe (2018) affirmed also that poor funding through budgetary allocation has been identified as the major reason for the rot and challenges in the education sector especially in tertiary institutions, which has led to frequent strikes by teaching and non-teaching staff since the early 1990s till date. Indeed, the Federal Government allocation to education in the last fourteen years has been stingy.

Table 1: Summary of Budget Allocation to the education sector from 2010-2023

Year	Total budget allocation (in Trillion)	National Education budget allocation (in Billion)	Allocation %
2010	4,608.68	339.6	7.73
2011	4,226.19	393.6	9.31
2012	4,749.10	463.3	9.76
2013	4,924.60	509.0	10.34
2014	4,698.19	565.8	12.04
2015	4,493.36	551.6	12.28
2016	6,060.68	480.28	7.92
2017	7,441.18	455.40	6.12
2018	9,120.33	651.23	7.14
2019	8,920	634.56	7.11
2020	1,0800	607.66	5.63
2021	1,3590	771.46	5.68
2022	1,7120	900.48	5.26
2023	2,1830	1080	4.95

Source: Federal Budget Office and Budget Research (2023)

From Table 1 above, it shows that the allocation to education keeps on increasing and decreasing at different intervals. In 2014, there was a significant increment of 1.7% from 2013, while 2015 there was an increment of 0.24 % from 2014 respectively, then declined in 2016 by 4.36% and in 2017 1.8% respectively in 2018, it increased by 1.02%, and decreases to 0.03% 2019, 1.48% in 2020, increases to 0.05% in 2021, decreases to 0.42% in 2022 and 0.31% in 2023 respectively. The education sector in Nigeria has been faced with inadequate budgetary allocation provisions challenges over the years.

Successive Governments had on different occasions promised to improve the sector, including an increased budgetary allocations to education, resolve long-standing issues with the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), and improve the quality of tertiary education but has failed.

Viewing the budgetary allocations for education between 2016 and 2023 indicates also that the government has never assigned up to 10 percent from the total national budget to the education sector. The allocation has declined from 7.92 percent in 2016 to 4.95 percent in 2023. In 2015, before Buhari was sworn in, a total of ₦551.6 billion from the total national budget (₦4,493.36) billion, translating to 12.28 percent of the budget, was for education. It decreased to 7.92 percent in Buhari's first budget in 2016. In 2017, 6.12 percent was earmarked for the education sector, showing a decrease from the percentage allocated in the previous year. In 2018, the allocation to education slightly increased again to 7.14 percent after a total of ₦651,23 billion was set aside for the education sector. It decreased again to 7.11 percent in 2019 as the Federal government allocated ₦634,56 billion to the sector. The budgetary allocation to education kept decreasing in spite of the vital nature of the sector and the clamouring of many stakeholders on the need for improvement in the sector. The situation was not different in 2020 as the Government again earmarked ₦607,66 billion, about 5.63 percent. In 2021, the allocation increased slightly to 5.68 as the government approved ₦771.46 billion. Similarly, the Federal government in 2022 budgeted ₦900,48 billion from its total allocation to education, which was about 5.26 percent of the amount, while in 2023, the administration earmarked ₦1,080 billion which is 4.95 percent from the total national budget of ₦2,1830 billion to the sector. However, increments in budget size are not felt in the education sector because the allocation is fluctuating below 10%, which added no value to skills learning in vocational education. The maximum and minimum allocation to education was 2015 and 2023 with 12.28% and 4.95% respectively against UNESCO recommendation. For a proper development to take place in Nigeria there must be a proper allocation to education to enhance creativity and productivity through science and technology.

2. Improving Budgetary Allocation to vocational and technical schools in Bayelsa State. Budgetary allocation is seen as a plan quantified in monetary terms prepared and approved for a specified period of time usually showing planned income to be generated and expended. In Nigeria, budget is normally presented by the executive arm of government to the legislative arm before it becomes appropriation bill (Ogungbenle & Edogiawerie, 2016).

Table 2 Summary of Budgetary Allocation to Science and Technology Education Board from Year 2020-2024

Year	Amount ₦
2020	7,307,981.77
2021	30,000,000.00
2022	30,000,000.00
2023	30,000,000.00
2024	50,000,000.00

Source: Budget Office, Ministry of Budget and Economic Planning, Yenagoa 2024

Table 2 above shows the budgetary allocation of ₦7,307,981.77 in year 2020 to ₦30,000,000.00 in 2021, 2022, 2023 respectively and increasing to ₦50,000,000.00 currently in 2024 for the technical schools across Bayelsa State. This is grossly inadequate to cater for the needs, programs and projects of vocational and technology education programs.

In Nigeria, the Vocational education programme can be funded through the following sources for increased productivity:

1. Government budgetary allocation. Government allocations are usually made in the budget to finance education from where it is disbursed accordingly to the needs of each level of educational setting. Frantic efforts have to be made to increase educational budgetary allocation to properly meet the needs of institutions. What is hindering development of school systems in the country, is government refusal to adequately and sufficiently allocate budgetary funds to meet the 26% UNESCO standard in education budgets. Proprietors of private schools, missionary schools and allied organizations appears to be doing better in funding their schools than the government owned schools. This is why non-governmental schools are expensive for learners to pass through than the government owned schools.

2. International organization. International organizations like United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the World Bank provides funds to assist developing countries to finance education through grants, scholarships donation of equipment, books, facilities etc.

3. Special grants. Federal government funds institutions by granting some form of grants through its agencies such as Tertiary education Trust Fund (TETFund) budgetary allocation to education which was established to generate funds from corporate organizations to help enhance development of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. These funds are channelled to building of libraries, medical centres, classrooms blocks, books, Computers, Vehicles, hostels, roads, Laboratory equipment, Machines, Scholarships, etc. The Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) has also help institutions through its donations in this direction.

4. Multi-national organizations. Funds also comes from multi-national organizations such as Nigeria Agip Oil Company (NAOC), Nigeria Liquefied National Gas (NLNG), TOTAL Fina Petroleum Nigeria Limited assist schools by donating projects, roads, scholarships, building, equipment, Vehicles, Laboratories etc.

5. Communities. Communities are often known for financing education through donating of land, facilities, equipment, security guards etc to safeguard life and property of the institutions.

6. School Fees. Payment of school fees, levies, tuition fees, ICT fees, levies, accommodation fees, development fees by learners is a way of funding and financing Vocational education. In other words, learners are stakeholders in the issue concerning funding of institutions especially in today's subvention problem given to institutions, school fees and other fees forms the major sources of funding and financing vocational education.

Funding Needs of Vocational Education for Increased Productivity

Vocational education has a lot to do with facilities, equipment, machines, etc. Provision of these facilities requires huge amount of funds which has made it to be identified as capital intensive

programme as such large amount of funds is required to finance the programme to increase its productivity. The following are some areas that needs huge funding:

1. Equipment and Machines. Vocational education programme is a skilled area of educating learners. Its effectiveness needs the use and application of modern facilities, equipment and machines, stimulation centres, entrepreneurship gardens and facilities etc. This also call for building of laboratories, studios, offices, workshops to help enhance teaching and learning as these activities are practical, so need adequate funds available to carter for their provision and maintenance.

2. Manpower development. Vocational education professionals need to be regularly trained to update their knowledge and skills. This does not end with attendance of seminars, workshops, books and Journal publications etc. Lecturers and Instructors need to further their studies for their certificates to be relevant to teach in the programme and increase productivity.

3. Salaries and allowances of teachers and allied workers. Lecturers in Vocational education programme are professionals and as such they need payment of salaries and allowances to be adequate to encourage them remain in the field, motivate and retain the job. When government funding is insufficient, lecturers may exit which can have negative impact and reduce productivity.

4. Student Industrial Works Experience Scheme (SIWES). This is the period students learn the practical aspects of the programme activities for which theory they have been taught in classrooms. Students here are expected to transfer their classroom knowledge to the office. This is a vocational programme whose objectives are for classrooms activities and as well as for office working experiences. Students on SIWES training are visited at their places of service by lecturers to ensure that there is compliance to meet the aim of the programme. It is expensive however to pay the allowances of both supervisors and the learners which institutions alone cannot afford, hence the assistance from Industrial Training Fund (ITF).

5. Provision of consumables or accessories. Machines and equipment needs regular maintenance consumables and accessories such as biro pens, paper tonner, ink etc for printers, photocopiers, fuel for vehicles, generators etc. Lack of these items makes these machines and equipment unproductive and cannot enhance the teaching and learning activities in institutions. Institutions departments need adequate funds to purchase these items to increase productivity. The present situation in our institutions where lecturers and students contribute hard earned money to savage situations to sustain programmes in institutions falls below expectations.

Challenges of Funding Vocational Education for Increased productivity

There are many challenges befalling funding of vocational education for increased productivity in Nigeria. These are:

1. Government posture to vocational education. Government has been very careless about vocational education programme in the present Nigeria despite its contributions to nation building. Interesting statements are made by government, creation of vocational training centers are established by government but no frantic efforts are made to implement these statements to better the programme. This lack of seriousness on the part of government has posed continuous set back and inadequate funding for the programme.

2. Control of Education. Nigerian Education in practice is centralized in terms of control. All certifying bodies are owned and controlled by the federal government and the Federal Ministry of Education. Like in the United States of America (USA), examination certifying bodies are owned and controlled by individual states. Which create room for competition to make quality education or a productive educational system. This calls for the creation of a separate ministry for vocational and technical education in 2009 (Ordu, 2017). Another issue is the literary degrees owners overseeing and controlling vocational education programmes which has to do with professional knowledge, Skills, Competencies based and degrees in vocational education field.

3. Societal perception of vocational education programme. The emergence of vocational education is directly traced to what was known as commercial colleges which were regarded as colleges for those learners that could not cope with the demands of public colleges. It was therefore termed as second-class school system for the second class youths of the community as a result of the huge financial involvement or the academic involvement (Ordu, 2017). The trend even though has changed with modernization in science and technology, the society's perception has not been completely erased. Secondly, there is the belief of people that vocational education programme degree holders end in the classroom of teaching. So those with this belief hold offices in government and politicize the issue of funding vocational education programmes thus hindering the funding and financing of the programme for increased productivity.

4. Non-recognition of its relevance. All over the world, vocational education is the wheel of progress, wealth creation and economic growth of nations. Unfortunately, in Nigeria, the programme is not recognized as a first class level programme that contributes to the national development and economic growth. Playing politics with funding of vocational education, which is skills base for self-reliance, the field of study will continue to encounter wastages of human and material resources in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Vocational education is a nation builder, life-wire, and a wheel of progress of any nation all over the world. In Nigeria, the programme has helped create many jobs and imparted many skills, knowledge and competencies to individuals for self-reliance, and increased productivity. Everywhere in the world, education has been proven to be a *sine qua-non* in the development of any nation. Practically, it is undisputable fact that poor state of vocational education in Nigeria continues to decline on a day-to-day basis due to inadequate funding. There is therefore the need to fund vocational education more with a view to sustaining the current position and at the same time positioning the sector for more robust performance to lift the productive capacity of the economy. The current budgetary allocations cannot achieve the needed or aspired economic growth and development. Apart from government funding vocational education, individuals, non-governmental organizations and cooperate bodies should as a matter of fact support the system.

Recommendations

Considering the skills, knowledge and competencies imparted by vocational education programmes in Nigeria, the following are recommended:

1. Government should increase funding and budgetary allocation sufficiently to the vocational education programme sector;
2. All individual citizens of Nigeria should recognize and see vocational education programme as a first-class educational programme that impart learners with skills, knowledge and competencies for self-reliant;
3. Only vocational education programme professionals with degrees in the field should control, administer and manned the management of the programme for efficient and for increased productivity as non-professionals will politicize funding and activities of the programme;
4. Government should endeavour to meet up or even strive to exceed the 26% benchmark allocation to education as recommended by UNESCO; and
5. Funding of vocational education should be supported by individuals, nongovernmental organizations and corporate bodies.

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